

Evaluating urban ventilation corridor: A lens from hyperlocal air pollution distribution through mobile monitoring

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GISRUK 2025

Summary

Urban morphology shapes the Urban Ventilation Corridor (UVC) and thus facilitates air pollution dispersion and reduces health hazards. However, traditional methods of evaluating UVC effects are not comprehensive due to the ignorance of the hyperlocal variation of environmental factors and human mobility. In this research, we first collect air pollution data by mobile monitoring in Glasgow, UK, extract the UVC, and finally evaluate air pollution exposure differences within and outside the UVC. The results show that UVC could effectively improve the pollution dispersion for PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀. Besides, encouraging small and fragmented buildings, roads, and vegetation patches could facilitate airflow and UVC formation.

KEYWORDS: Urban morphology; Surface roughness; Urban Ventilation Corridor (UVC); Air pollution; Mobile monitoring

1. Introduction

More than 99% of the population's exposure to air pollution is above WHO guidelines and 4.2 million deaths are attributed to ambient air pollution each year (WHO, 2024). Fortunately, great urban ventilation could facilitate pollution dispersion and alleviate potential health hazards (Yang et al., 2020). This need arises from the desire to gain detailed insights into the distribution of urban ventilation, evaluate its effects on air pollution dispersion, and facilitate effective management strategies.

A surge of research focuses on leveraging the Urban Ventilation Corridor (UVC), the passages that promote peripheral air entering the city and speeding up the city airflow (Werner, 1979), to characterize the ventilation conditions in complex urban environments. Unlike accurate simulation of airflow around buildings in wind tunnel tests and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations, the GIS-based morphological analysis is an empirical model based on the relationship between urban morphological parameters and experimental wind data, which are suitable for analysis at the city level and can quickly and effectively analyze urban ventilation environments (Peng et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019; Yang & Li, 2015).

Therefore, this study has three major contributions: 1). Leverage both 2D and 3D urban morphology to characterize the urban surface roughness and extract UVC; 2). Validate the effects of UVC on hyperlocal air pollution dispersion by comparing the differences in pollution concentration between UVC and non-UVC areas based on mobile monitoring; 3). Predict the air pollution distribution through spatially explicit machine learning models and interpret the effects of urban form on UVC distribution. We anticipate our assessment of UVC to be towards inclusive and equitable practices for

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localizing the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) with sensitivity to public health (SDG 3), intra-urban inequalities (SDG 10), and sustainable cities (SDG 11).

2. Research area and data

Glasgow, the third largest city in the UK, has a population of around 0.6 million at the core of a city region with 1.8 million people. A total travel distance of 2.22 billion miles was made on its roads in 2023 (Transport, 2023). Moreover, Glasgow has a unique urban morphology characterized by a blend of historic and modern architecture and a distinct street layout, featuring a grid system in the city center and a more irregular pattern in the surrounding areas (GlasgowTimes, 2023), which shapes the complicated impacts of the built environment on the ventilation corridor. Therefore, it is crucial to analyze how urban ventilation in Glasgow could affect air pollution dispersion and environmental justice. Table 1 summarizes all datasets used in this study.

Table 1 Summary of datasets

Name	Spatial Unit	Periods	Temporal granularity	Spatial coverage	Access	Source
Air pollution	Point	2024	Secondly	Glasgow	Safeguarded	Mobile monitoring
Local meteorology	Station	2024	Hourly	UK	Open	<u>UK Met Office</u>
Traffic count	Station	2024	Annually	UK	Open	<u>Department of Transport</u>
CCTV	Station	2024	30-minute	Glasgow	Open	<u>UBDC</u>
Land use	100m Grid	2022	--	UK	Open	<u>Digimap</u>
SIMD index	DataZone	2020	Annually	Scotland	Open	<u>Scottish Government</u>
2D and 3D urban morphology	100m grid	2024	--	Glasgow	Derived	--

2.1 UVC extraction

To find the least-cost path of surface roughness, we apply the LCVC (Least Cumulative Ventilation Cost) method to extract UVC (Xie et al., 2020). The formula of LCVC can be written in Equation 1:

$$C_{s \rightarrow d} = C_{s \rightarrow m} + C_{d \rightarrow m}, \quad \text{where } C_{d \rightarrow m} = C_{m \rightarrow d} \quad (1)$$

$$\Rightarrow C_m = C_{m \rightarrow s} + C_{m \rightarrow d}$$

where s is the air inlet, d is the air outlet, and m is a point on an LCP between s and d . The values of LCVC from m to d and from d to m are equal ($C_{d \rightarrow m} = C_{m \rightarrow d}$) along the LCP because the values are equal when the differences of θ is π for calculating the ventilation resistance. Therefore, the cost of any point in the ventilation resistance surface C_m can be expressed as the sum of the cost to the inlet $C_{m \rightarrow s}$ and outlet $C_{m \rightarrow d}$.

3. Results

3.1 Air pollution distribution

As shown in Figure 1, most polluted areas are distributed around middle and southern Glasgow with dense buildings (e.g., restaurants), congested traffic, and worse ventilation. For example, during data collection, we found that the pollution level peaks when we pass restaurants' backyards, particularly with grease ducts. These areas are usually distributed in narrow streets surrounded by high buildings (large AR) with bad ventilation. In contrast, the air quality is better in the northeastern part, which has a large coverage of greenspace and better ventilation.

Figure 1. Mobile monitoring of air quality (aggregated by minute)

3.2 UVC distribution

Figure 2 shows the distribution of UVC according to the dominant wind direction (east to west) from 01/03/2024 to 31/04/2024. We further classify the UVC into three categories according to the number of least-cost paths (N_Paths) from each wind inlet to outlet: major ($N_Paths \geq 13$), secondary ($7 < N_Paths < 13$), and Tertiary ($N_Paths \leq 7$). The thresholds are set according to the number of inlet (13) and outlet (7) points. Intervals of wind inlets and outlets are set to 200m, which contain at least two grids of FAI. As can be seen, the major UVCs extend from the Middle East to the Southwest with the best ventilation, therefore, eastern Glasgow enjoys better air quality (Figure 1). The secondary UVCs are distributed in the northern and southern regions, and the tertiary UVCs spread along the northeastern and southeastern parts. Limited UVCs have been identified in the city center due to higher surface roughness (e.g., larger values of FAI and AR) resulting in worse ventilation and air quality.

Figure 2. UVC according to the dominant wind direction

3.2 UVC evaluation

Figure 3 summarizes the mean value of PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, and PM_{10} within and outside the UVC areas for different collection routes and periods. For the “All routes” group (combined all data), air pollutants are lower in the UVC area than in the non-UVC area. These differences are more marked for Route 1 (North), Route 2 (West), and morning rush hour. It confirms that great ventilation could improve the air quality in dense urban settings. Even though such differences are smaller for evening rush hour, this could be attributed to congested traffic (impeding the airflow) during this period. Furthermore, UVC could facilitate the dispersion of large particles better than small particles for most groups (i.e., Route 2, Route 3, morning rush hour, Weekdays, and Weekends). For example, there are 0.60 ug/m^3 , 0.92 ug/m^3 , and 1.50 ug/m^3 reduction for PM_{10} , $PM_{2.5}$, and PM_{10} , respectively, for Route 2. For Route 4 (Southeastern), air quality is slightly better for the non-UVC area. The reason could be that Route 4 is closer to industrial land uses in southern Glasgow, which also suggests that mobile monitoring could better reveal the exposure hazards of air pollutants on hyperlocal scales.

Figure 3. Mean value of air pollution concentration within and outside UVC under different conditions

4. Conclusions

Air pollution is one of the major environmental hazards and a hot topic for public health, particularly in high-density urban environments. Fortunately, great urban ventilation could facilitate pollution dispersion and alleviate health hazards. This paper investigates how and to what extent UVC could help to disperse hyperlocal air pollution concentration through mobile monitoring in Glasgow, UK. The results reveal that UVC is effective in improving air quality for PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀, particularly in northern and western Glasgow and the morning rush hour. From the planning perspective, encouraging the small and fragmented buildings, roads, and vegetation patches could facilitate the airflow and formation of UVC. Therefore, this study provides effective ways of evaluating UVC and provides insightful guidance on future urban planning to identify effective urban morphology to promote steady airflow and UVC formation.

5. Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the internal research grant from the University of Glasgow and all other contributors, other members of the Urban Big Data Center (UBDC) for providing the data service, and all volunteers for data collection and calibration during these two months. Prof Qunshan Zhao has received the ESRC's ongoing support for the Urban Big Data Centre (UBDC) [ES/L011921/1 and ES/S007105/1], and Royal Society International Exchange Scheme [IEC\NSFC\223042]. The authors want to thank the anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments and suggestions on an earlier version of this manuscript.

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Dr. Qunshan Zhao joined the University of Glasgow in May 2019 as a Lecturer (Assistant Professor) in Urban Analytics in Urban Studies and Urban Big Data Centre (UBDC) in the School of Social and Political Sciences. He was promoted to Senior Lecturer (Associate Professor) in August 2022, and to Professor in August 2024. He holds both a Ph.D. and an M.A. in Geography/GIScience from Arizona State University in the USA and a B.E. in Remote Sensing, Photogrammetry, and GIS from Wuhan University in China. Prior to coming to the UK, he was a postdoctoral research associate in the Knowledge Exchange for Resilience (KER) and Spatial Analysis Research Center (SPARC) at Arizona State University.

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